

significantly less than to urea at 60 and 120 kg N/ha. Poultry manure at 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha produced rice grain yield equivalent to that by 37, 96, and 168 kg urea N/ha, respectively. On the basis of N uptake, poultry manure N was 80% as efficient as urea N at all rates of application.

Urea and manure differ in increasing

rice grain yield at 60 kg N/ha, perhaps because at low application rates, sufficient manure N might not be mineralized for critical growth stages of rice. No significant differences in uptake of P and K by rice were observed between urea and poultry manure.

A residual effect of poultry manure N was shown by wheat grown after rice

only at the highest rate of application (see table). The residual effect of the manure in supplying P to wheat was conspicuous, both through Olsen's available P and a significant response of wheat to 26 kg P/ha in plots where poultry manure had been applied to rice at 0, 60, and 120 kg N/ha. □

Nitrogen-fixing potential of blue-green algae (BGA) from Kerala ricefields

K. Joseph, N.R. Nair, K.P. Rajaram, D. Alexander, and K. Anilakumar, Kerala Agricultural University, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi, India

We studied the effect of P and Mo on N fixation by a mixture of BGA in 1-liter beakers containing 200 g each of air-dried soil from Trichur district (pH 4.56, CEC 21 meq/100 g, C 3.2196, N 31%) brought to neutrality by adding calcium carbonate at 700 kg/ha. Two levels of Mo (0.2 and 0.4 ppm) and 2 levels of P (4 and 8 kg/ha) were used, in 9 treatments replicated 3 times.

BGA crust at 10 kg/ha was inoculated. The beakers were kept in the open for 3 wk with water level

Effect of Mo and P on N fixation^a by BGA in Kerala ricefields, India.

	N fixation ^b (kg/ha)			Mean
	No Mo (control)	0.2 ppm Mo	0.4 ppm Mo	
No P (control)	6.3	6.3	12.5	8.4
4 kg P/ha	12.5	15.7	9.4	12.5
8 kg P/ha	9.4	12.5	18.8	13.6
Mean	9.4	11.5	13.6	

^aTotal N after 3 wk - initial N. ^bCD (0.05) for comparison of Mo and P = 3.16.

Confidence limit for means = ± 2.109

CD (0.05) for comparison of combinations = 5.48

Confidence limit for cells = ± 3.653

maintained at 5-10 cm above soil level. Then the soil was allowed to dry and the BGA crust was incorporated. Total N was determined by the microKjeldahl method.

Both Mo and P had favorable influence on N fixation. The combination treatment 8 kg P/ha and

0.4 ppm Mo fixed the largest amount of N (see table). At 8 kg P/ha, each additional Mo level improved N fixation by BGA. On average, addition of 0.4 ppm Mo increased N fixation by 44% over the control; addition of 8 kg P/ha increased N fixation by 62% over the control. □

Rice-based Cropping Systems

Effect of an interim summer crop in a rice - wheat rotation

M.S. Maskina, B. Singh, and Y. Singh, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

During the summer (May-Jun) in the Punjab, a shortduration crop is grown between the dry and wet season main crops. This crop could be a cereal fodder, a pulse, or a green manure.

Green manuring is gaining importance with increasing costs of

fertilizers and threats of pollution. In rice, green manuring with sesbania has been successfully used to supplement fertilizer N. On the other hand, growing a cereal fodder might deplete available nutrients and adversely affect rice yield. We conducted a field experiment 1984-85 to study the effect of summer maize *Zea mays* fodder, mungbean *Phaseolus aureus* pulse, cowpea *Vigna sinensis*, sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea*, and sesbania *Sesbania aculeata* green manure (GM) crops on the following rice crop.

Soil was a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept), alkaline (pH 8.5), with 0.40% organic C, 7.5 kg available P/ha, and 81 kg available K/ha.

Crops were planted the first week of May. Maize was fertilized with 120 kg N/ha applied in 2 splits and harvested for fodder at 2 mo. Mature mungbean pods were picked. Mungbean residue and the 3 green manure crops were incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice. N was applied to rice at 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha in 3 equal splits (1/3 at transplanting, 1/3 3 wk and 1/3 6 wk

Table 1. Effect of green manure (GM), mungbean residues, maize fodder, and N application on rice grain yield (t/ha). Ludhiana, India, 1984-85.

Crop grown before rice	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	0	60	120	180
		kg N	kg N	kg N
Fallow	2.5	4.6	5.6	6.6
Sesbania GM	5.8	6.4	—	—
Cowpea (GM)	6.0	6.8	—	—
Sunn hemp (GM)	5.8	6.8	—	—
Mungbean (pulse)	5.1	6.2	—	—
Maize (fodder)	2.2	4.5	5.7	6.5
LSD (P=0.05)	0.7			

Table 2. Residual effect of GM, mungbean residues, and maize fodder grown before rice on succeeding wheat crop. Ludhiana, India, 1984-85.

Crop grown before rice	N applied to wheat (kg/ha)	Wheat yield (t/ha)
Fallow	120	4.7
Sesbania (GM)	90	4.3
Cowpea (GM)	90	4.2
Sunn hemp	90	4.1
Mungbean (pulse)	90	4.2
Maize (fodder)	120	4.9
LSD (P=0.05)		0.4

after transplanting). A basal dose of 13-13 kg PK/ha was applied. The residual effect of these treatments was studied on the succeeding dry season wheat crop.

At 60 d growth, sesbania and sunn hemp had produced the most dry matter (4.9 and 5.3 t/ha), followed by cowpea and mungbean (3.8 and 3.2 t/ha). Sesbania contained 97 kg N/ha, sunn hemp 101 kg N, cowpea 75 kg N and mungbean 65 kg N. Mungbean also produced 600 kg beans/ha. Maize fodder yielded 5.8 t dry matter/ha and removed 70 kg N/ha from the soil.

When no fertilizer N was applied, rice grain yields with sesbania, sunn hemp, and cowpea were similar and averaged 15% higher than with mungbean residue and 141% higher than fallow treatments (Table 1). With 60 kg N/ha, rice grain yield with all green manure crops and with mungbean residue were on a par, 36-48% higher than fallow plots. These yields were comparable with yields from fallow plots receiving 180 kg N/ha.

None of the green manure crops

incorporated in rice exhibited residual effects on the succeeding wheat crop (Table 2). Wheat yield in fallow plots with 120 kg N/ha was significantly

higher than in green manured plots supplied with 90 kg N/ha. Wheat yield after maize fodder was no different from that in fallow plots. □

Intercropping rice and pigeonpea

P.K. Mahapatra, N. Hati, and D. Satpathy, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa, India

The response of pigeonpea + rice to varying levels of N was studied in a randomized block design replicated four times during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons in a lateritic soil of sandy loam texture (pH 5.3, 0.04% total N, 8 kg available P/ha, 125 kg available K/ha, CEC 3.8 meq/100 g).

Pigeonpea cultivar R-60 (180 d) was sown as the base crop in twin rows with an inter-twin-row distance of 90 cm and plant-to-plant spacing of 30 cm. Spacing and seed rate (20 kg/ha) for pigeonpea alone and intercropped pigeonpea were the same.

Rice cultivar DR-92 (90 d) was direct seeded in 15-cm rows in the interspace

of 90 cm. Row spacing for rice alone was 15 cm. Rice alone was sown at 100 kg seed/ha and intercropped rice at 75 kg seed/ha. Row ratio of pigeonpea to rice was 25 and the land area ratio was 1:0.75.

N was applied at 30, 45, 60, and 75 kg/ha; 10 kg N of each N level, plus 18 kg P and 17 kg K were applied at sowing for rice alone and the intercrops. The remaining N was applied to rice in 2 equal splits at 20 and 40 d after seeding. Pigeonpea alone received a single basal dose of 20-18-17 kg NPK/ha.

Intercropped rice showed no response to N. Mean grain yields were 2.0 t/ha for rice alone and 1.2 t/ha for intercropped rice. Mean yields of pigeonpea were 1.3 t/ha for the monocrop and 1.1 t/ha for the intercrop. The mean land equivalent ratio was 1.4, indicating considerable increase in resource use efficiency. □

Response of rice to NPK in long-term jute - rice - wheat sequence

B. C. Mandal and B. P. Sarkar, Jute Agricultural Research Institute, Barrackpore 743101, West Bengal, India

Table 1. NPK applied to jute - rice - wheat cropping sequence. Barrackpore, West Bengal, India, 1972-84.

Treatment	NPK (kg/ha)					
	Rice and wheat			Jute		
	N	P	K	N	P	K
T1 50% optimum ^a NPK	60	13	25	30	6.5	25
T2 100% optimum NPK	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T3 150% optimum NPK	180	39	75	90	19.5	75
T4 100% NPK + hand weeding	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T5 100% NPK + ZnSO ₄ for wheat only	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T6 100% optimum NP	120	26	—	60	13.0	—
T7 100% optimum N	120	—	—	60	—	—
T8 100% NPK + farmyard manure for jute only	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T9 100% optimum NPK + chemical weeding	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T10 Control (no fertilizer)	—	—	—	—	—	—

^aOptimum NPK based on initial soil test.

The cropping sequence jute - rice - wheat is widely practiced in the eastern region of India, especially in the New Gangetic alluvial tracts. We laid out a long-term fertilizer experiment on 1 ha of recent